

COMPARATIVE EFFICACY OF SALICYLIC ACID AND ASCORBIC ACID SEED PRIMING ON MORPHO-PHYSIOLOGICAL ATTRIBUTES OF MAIZE UNDER ZINC TOXICITY

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ABSTRACT

Zinc is essential micronutrient for cereal crops like wheat, rice and maize. In plants it plays a vital role in many enzyme activities and metabolic processes although plants need zinc in small amounts. However enhanced levels of Zn in soils are phytotoxic, cause several structural as well as functional abnormalities, eventually weakening the plant performance. Plant growth regulators are chemical messenger that improve plant parameters under control and stress conditions. A pot experiment was performed in Department of Botany University of Balochistan, Quetta. Maize plant grown under Zinc stress (300 μ M) and seeds were primed with PGRs (SA and AsA). After 15 days of seed germination, seedlings were subjected to zinc stress, after 1 week of Zn stress plant was harvested to analyze the morpho-physiological attributes. Zinc stress inhibited the maize growth, physiological parameters, metabolites and nutrients. However, PGRs improved the growth and all other parameters of Maize. Results revealed that seed priming with both SA and AsA significantly improved germination rate, plant growth attributes and biomass compared with non-primed stressed maize. Primed plants also exhibited enhanced physiological performance suggesting better stress tolerance mechanism. Overall the study concludes that SA and AsA seed priming can be adopted as a simple and effective strategy to ameliorate zinc toxicity and improve Maize performance under zinc stress.

INTRODUCTION

Zinc is an essential micronutrient for cereal crops like Wheat, rice and maize. In plants it play a vital role in many enzyme activities and metabolic processes although plants need zinc in small amounts (Broadley *et al.*, 2007). Zinc is involved in carbohydrate metabolism, hormone regulation (like auxins), pollen development, maintaining cell membranes and helping crops resist certain diseases (Ayyar *et al.*, 2020). Seed priming with PGRs like Salicylic acid and Ascorbic Acid involve partially hydrating seeds to trigger metabolic processes necessary for germination without allowing the seed to actually sprout (Ahmad, I., 2012). This technique is an effective short-term solution to help seed cope with drought and other stress conditions improving seedlings emergence and plant establishment. Seed priming with PGRs ascorbic acid, salicylic acid significantly improved the growth, physiological and yield related problems of maize (Ahmad *et al.*, 2014).

Seed priming with ASA and SA mitigated adverse effect by enhancing seedling, shoot and root development. This may result from ability of PGRs priming agents to protect photosynthesis and CO₂ fixation. Priming with PGRs resulted in a lower root to shoot ratio compared to non-primed plants. Previous studies have also confirmed that priming with SA and ASA boosts antioxidant enzyme activity in cereal crops (Sedghi *et al.*, 2010).

Seed that have been primed with Salicylic acid and Ascorbic acid often germinate faster and more uniformly this improvement is mainly because priming shortens the initial water phase promotes buildup of substances that aid germination and helps seeds adjust their internal water balance (Ahmad *et al.*, 2014). More recent research supports the idea these compounds at low concentration improve antioxidant capacity under stress, ultimately, seed priming with PGRs like SA and ASA led to significant improvements in grain yield and related traits. This yield increase may be attributed to enhance membrane stability (Hasanuzzaman *et al.*, 2020).

Salicylic acid gets its name from the Latin word *Salix* meaning willow tree which is known natural source of this compound. It is widely distributed across the plant kingdom and is classified as a plant hormone (Shatpathy *et al.*, 2018). SA plays a significant role in regulating plant metabolism and influences various aspects of plant growth and development. It also activates defense responses, helping plants tolerate both biotic and abiotic stresses, primarily through the regulation of antioxidant enzymes. Seed priming has been shown to enhance stress tolerance in plants, likely by gene expression related to stress response (Shatpathy *et al.*, 2018).

Ascorbic acid is a crucial metabolite involve in processes such as cell division and osmotic regulation and it plays a significant role during early phases of seed germination. ASA act as powerful antioxidant, helping to balance the production and removal of reactive oxygen species in the plant (Farooq *et al.*, 2013). Applying ASA externally has been shown to boost the plant internal ASA content. Therefore, treating seeds with ASA through priming could enhance cereal crops (Wheat, Rice, and Maize). Ability to establish itself and regulate growth patterns (Farooq *et al.*, 2013).

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is a major crop with high yield potential and is considered the third most important cereal in Pakistan (Ahmad *et al.*, 2014). It is grown two times in a year during the spring

and autumn season's mainly for producing grain, but it is also used as animal feed and fodder (Arif *et al.*, 2011). Maize is a warm-weather crop that can grow in different climates, from hot tropical areas to cooler temperate zones. However, it grows best where the night temperature stays above 15°C, because the temperature lower than this can stop plant from growing. Early growth stages of maize are especially affected by cold weather. When temperature fall below 15°C, it can harm the plant by damaging its cell membranes, photosynthetic system, and enzymes needed for growth (Jompuk *et al.*, 2005). This damage is often caused by higher levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which can lead to weak seedlings and poor crop establishment (Guan *et al.*, 2009).

Zea mays has long been a key crop worldwide not just as a food but also as a model plant for genetic research for over a century scientists have used maize to study genetics and evolution making it one of the most studied plant (Woodhouse *et al.*, 2024). Maize classified as C₄ plant, utilizes nutrients with high efficiency to generate biomass and food. Its contribution to the diet of nearly three billion individuals globally underscores its nutritional importance. It is widely cultivated in temperate climates. The maize represents the primarily edible portion of plant and is valued for its high nutritional content. Maize also offers a wide spectrum of essential vitamins. These includes Vitamin C and K as well as several B-complex vitamins such as thiamine (B₁), Niacin (B₂), riboflavin (B₃), pantothenic acid (B₅), Pyridoxine (B₆) and folic acid (Rouf Shah *et al.*, 2016). The main objectives of this study are as under

- To evaluate the comparative efficacy of selected signaling molecules in alleviating Zinc toxicity in Maize.
- To evaluate the best exogenous treatment for Maize in ameliorating Zinc toxicity across the altitudinal gradient.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Experiment layout

A pot experiment was conducted using 1kg soil pots. Seeds of maize was primed for (12 hours) with SA, AsA, in comparison to water and no priming. Seed was sown at 1inchdepth. The design of experiment was CRD with 3 replicates. After 15days of seed germination, seedlings were subjected to zinc stress, after 1week of Zn stress plant was harvested to analyze the morpho-physiological attributes.

Sources of Seeds

Maize seeds (*Zea mays*) was supplied by the ARI, Quetta.

Determination of Morphological Attributes

The following growth parameters of maize was recorded. (Root and shoot length in cm, root and shoot fresh weight in gram and dry biomass at after at 65-75°C, number of leaves per plant, was recorded).

Physio-biochemical Attributes

Determination of Photosynthetic Pigments

Maize photosynthetic pigments were extracted by taking (0.1g) of leaf sample and grinded 1-2m 80% acetone and kept final volume up 10mL by using 80% acetone. Pigments absorbance was measured at 663, 645nm was measured against 80% acetone that kept as blank. Arnon (1949) formula was used for estimation of chlorophyll and represented as μg of chl/g FWT.

$$\text{Chl a} = \{(1.27 \times A_{663} - 2.69 \times A_{645})\} \times V/1000 \times W$$

$$\text{Chl b} = \{(22.9 \times A_{645}) - 4.68 \times A_{663}\} \times V/1000 \times W$$

Method of Kirk and Allen, (1965), was used for carotenoid estimation and described in units of its absorbance as A₄₈₀ FWT/g.

$$A_{\text{car}} / 480 / \text{wt of leaf} = A_{480} + 0.114 \cdot (A_{663} - 0.638 \times A_{645}) / 2500 \times 1000$$

Determination of anthocyanin

The formula of Stark and Wray (1989) was for the determination of the anthocyanin contents in both root and shoot the 0.1 g sample was taken to determine the anthocyanin contents. Sample was extracted in (1-2mL) of acidified methanol that was placed in water bath for at 50°C for an hour. The absorbance was noted 535nm by spectrophotometer. The acidified methanol was used as blank.

Determination of Soluble Sugars

Method of Yashida et al., (1976) examined to determine the soluble sugar of both shoot and root. About 0.1 g was boiled for an hour in (5mL) of distilled water. One mL from the extract was taken and diluted by adding (9mL) distilled water, and 0.5mL from this extract was taken and 5mL of anthrone reagent was added. Taken sample mixture and put in water bath for about 20 min at 90°C. Reading was noted at 620nm using spectrophotometer and distilled water kept as blank.

Determination of Soluble Phenolics

Method developed by Julkunen-titto, (1985) was used to determine soluble phenolics of plant sample of (0.1g) was taken and grinded into (1-2 mL) of 80% acetone. In a test tube taken 1 mL distilled water followed by the addition of 100 μL of the sample and 0.5 mL Folin phenol reagent, then 2.5mL of 20% Na₂CO₃ (Sodium carbonate) was added. Reading at 745nm was noted using spectrophotometer with 80% acetone as blank.

Nutrients Analysis

The analysis of nutrients was carried out to record the differences among treatments only Sulphur. Plant sample was firstly oven dried and then was digested in nitric acid.

Statistical Analysis

Recorded data was analyzed by the help of "STATISTIX 8.1" while graphs and mean, standard deviation was calculated using MS. EXCEL.

Lab Facilities Available

All lab work was done in the Department of Botany, UoB, Quetta.

Figure: 1. Experimental layout

RESULTS

Morphological attributes:

Data regarding the shoot length of *Zea mays* under zinc stress conditions revealed statistically significant among different treatments. The largest shoot length was observed in treatment of ASA 0.4mM control (42.11 cm) however the smallest shoot length observed in the treatment of control Zn stress (31.33 cm) (**Figure 1A**). Data regarding the root length of *Zea mays* under zinc stress conditions revealed statistically non-significant results among different treatments. The largest root length was observed in treatment of ASA 0.6mM control (19.8 cm) however the smallest root length observed in the treatment of H₂O primed Zn stress (9.96 cm) (**Figure 1B**). Data regarding the number of leaves of *Zea mays* under zinc stress conditions revealed statistically non-significant among different treatments. The highest number of leaves was observed in treatment of ASA 0.6mM control and Control (2.667) however the smallest root length observed in the treatment of ASA 0.4mM Zn stress (1.33) (**Figure 1C**). Data regarding the shoot fresh weight of *Zea mays* under zinc stress conditions revealed statistically significant among different treatments. The maximum SFW was observed in treatment of SA 200 μ M control (1.34 g) however the minimum SFW observed in the treatment of H₂O Zn stress (0.66 g) (**Figure 1D**). Data regarding the root fresh weight of *Zea mays* under zinc stress conditions revealed statistically significant results among different treatments. The maximum root fresh weight was observed in treatment of ASA 0.6mM control (0.55 g) however the smallest root length observed in the treatment of ASA 0.4mM Zn stress (0.16 g) (**Figure 1E**). Data regarding the root dry weight of *Zea mays* under zinc stress conditions revealed statistically non-significant results among different treatments. The maximum RDW was observed in treatment of ASA 0.6mM control (0.0633) however the minimum RDW observed in the treatment of ASA 0.4mM Zn stress (0.0133) (**Figure 1F**). Data regarding the shoot dry weight of *Zea mays* under zinc stress

conditions revealed statistically non-significant results among different treatments. The maximum SDW was observed in treatment of H₂O primed control (0.09) however the minimum SDW observed in the treatment of SA 250 μ M Zn stress (0.0133) (**Figure 1G**).

Fig 1: Growth parameter; (A) Shoot length (B) Root length (C) Number of leaves (D) Shoot Fresh Weight (E) Root Fresh Weight (F) Shoot dry weight (G) Root dry weight of *Zea mays* under Zinc stress and Control conditions.

Photosynthetic pigments:

Data regarding the chlorophyll a of *Zea mays* under zinc stress conditions revealed statistically non-significant results among different treatments. The maximum chlorophyll a was observed in treatment of ASA 0.6mM Zn. stress (3.84 m) however the minimum chlorophyll a observed in the treatment of

Control (control) (3.11) (**Figure 2A**). Data regarding the chlorophyll b of *Zea mays* under zinc stress conditions revealed statistically non-significant results among different treatments. The maximum chlorophyll b was observed in treatment of control zinc stress (1.44) however the minimum chlorophyll b observed in the treatment of H₂O primed control (1.06) (**Figure 2B**). Data regarding the carotenoids of *Zea mays* under zinc stress conditions revealed statistically non-significant results among different treatments. The maximum carotenoids were observed in treatment of control zinc stress (1.13) however the minimum carotenoids observed in the treatment of H₂O primed control (0.86) (**Figure 2C**).

Figure 2: Photosynthetic Pigments; (A) Chlorophyll a (B) Chlorophyll b (C) Carotenoids of *Zea mays* under Zinc stress and Control conditions

Metabolites

Data regarding the shoot soluble phenolics of *Zea mays* under zinc stress conditions revealed statistically significant results among different treatments. The maximum SSP was observed in treatment of SA 250µM Zn stress (29.9) however the minimum SSP length observed in the treatment of ASA 0.6mM control (17.2) (**Figure 3A**). Data regarding the root soluble phenolics of *Zea mays* under zinc stress conditions revealed statistically non-significant results among different treatments. The largest RSP was observed in treatment of ASA 0.4mM Zn stress (35.4) however the smallest RSP observed in the treatment of SA 200µM control (20.3) (**Figure 3B**). Data regarding the shoot soluble sugars of *Zea mays* under zinc stress conditions revealed statistically non-significant results among different treatments. The maximum SSS was observed in treatment of SA 200µM (26.6) however SA 200µM the minimum SSS observed in the treatment of control (control) (11.1). (**Figure 3C**). Data regarding the root soluble sugars of *Zea mays* under zinc stress conditions revealed statistically non-significant results among different treatments. The maximum RSS was observed in treatment of SA 250µM Zn stress (24.9) however the minimum RSS observed in the treatment of control (control) (18.06) (**Figure 3D**). Data regarding the shoot anthocyanin of *Zea mays* under zinc stress conditions revealed statistically significant results among different treatments. The maximum SAC was observed in treatment of SA 200µM Zn stress (0.58) however the minimum SAC observed in the treatment of control (control) (0.12) (**Figure 3E**). Data regarding the root anthocyanin of *Zea*

mays under zinc stress conditions revealed statistically significant results among different treatments. The maximum RAC was observed in treatment of control Zn stress (0.97) however the minimum RAC observed in the treatment of SA 200 μ M control (0.31) (**Figure 3F**).

Figure 3: Metabolites; (A) Shoot soluble phenolics **(B)** Root Soluble Phenolics **(C)**Shoot Soluble Sugar **(D)** Root Soluble Sugar **(E)** Shoot Anthocyanin **(F)** Root Anthocyanin

Nutrients:

Data regarding the shoot sulphate of *Zea mays* under zinc stress conditions revealed statistically significant results among different treatments. The maximum SS was observed in treatment of ASA 0.6mM Zn stress (1.31) however the minimum SS observed in the treatment of SA (200 μ M) Control (0.64) (**Figure 4A**). Data regarding the root sulphate of *Zea mays* under zinc stress conditions revealed statistically significant results among different treatments. The maximum SS was observed in treatment of SA 250 μ M Zn stress (1.2) however the minimum SS observed in the treatment of H₂O Primed Control (0.82) (**Figure 4B**).

Figure 4: Sulphate; (A) Shoot sulphate **(B)** Root Sulphate

DISCUSSION

Most crops need zinc in the range of 30 to 2000 μ g/g of dry matter to stay healthy however excess concentration of zinc in the soil is toxic to plant leading to various structural and physiological disturbances that ultimately impair the plant growth and overall performance (Kaur & Garg, 2021). Seed priming with PGRs ascorbic acid, salicylic acid significantly improved the growth, physiological and yield related problems of maize (Ahmad *et al.*, 2014). In this present study zinc stress had a clear negative impact on the morphological attributes of *Zea mays* seedlings particularly reducing root and shoot length, NOL and root and shoot weight. The general reduction in plant growth reflects the harmful effect of zinc toxicity on early seedling development. However, the application of PGRs through seed priming particularly with SA and ASA helped to improve the morphological attributes thus mitigating the adverse impact of zinc stress. These findings are similar to previously published research on lead stress (Zanganeh *et al.*, 2019) where growth attributes were also suppressed in maize under lead stress. While protective effects of PGRs were reported under Pb stress having visible improvement in shoot growth and fresh weight although the changes in root growth and dry weight were not significant.

Zinc toxicity leads to a decline in net photosynthesis though the exact underlying cause remains uncertain. This reduction may stem from limitations in mesophyll or stomatal conductance, increased respiratory activity, disruption of photochemical processes and biochemical pathways (Kaur & Garg, 2021). However, Priming with PGRs resulted in a lower root to shoot ratio compared to non-primed plants. Previous studies have also confirmed that priming with SA and ASA boosts antioxidant enzyme activity in cereal crops (Sedghi *et al.*, 2010). In this study zinc stress negatively influenced photosynthetic pigment levels in *Zea mays* including chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and carotenoids although the differences among treatments were statistically non-significant. Despite the lack of significant variation noticeable reduction in pigment content were observed in several treatments. However, the seed priming with PGRs particularly SA and ASA appeared to mitigate the negative effect if zinc stress on pigment contents. Primed plants generally maintained higher levels of chlorophyll a, b as well as carotenoid under Zn stress compared to unprimed ones. These results are similar with previous studies (Kaur & Garg, 2021) who reported zinc induced reduction in photosynthesis to multiple physiological disruptions, elevated zn levels can restrict photosynthetic carbon fixation by interfering with CO₂ diffusion into chloroplast.

Zinc is a vital micronutrient that supports immune development and cognitive functions in humans, it also plays a significant role in plants (Ayyar *et al.*, 2020). However excessive zinc accumulation in soil can be toxic to plants leading to a range of structural and functional disruptions that ultimately impair plant growth and productivity (Khudsar *et al.*, 2004; Vaillant *et al.* 2005). While seed priming especially with SA and ASA enhances seed germination and seedling emergence (Ahmad, 2012). In this study physiological parameters of *Zea mays* seedlings including shoot and root soluble sugars and root and shoot soluble phenolics and Anthocyanin were influenced by zinc stress and priming with plant growth regulators such as SA and ASA. Also shoot soluble sugar and

root soluble sugar did not show statistically significant differences suggesting a mild activation of phenolic metabolism as a protective response in contrast root and shoot soluble phenolics were constantly increased under stress. These results are similar to the previous study of (M’Rah *et al.*, 2023) who reported that Zn treatment promoted the accumulation of total soluble sugars and proline in maize tissues in concentration dependent manner particularly in roots.

In this study Sulphate content in both shoots and roots of *Zea mays* was generally reduced under zinc stress particularly in unprimed control plants indicating that zinc stress affected the Sulphur uptake. However, seed priming with plant growth regulators` particularly SA and ASA led to an improvement in Sulphur content mitigating the zinc stress. This suggests that although zinc stress negatively influence Sulphur accumulation. These findings are similar with (Reskin, 2023) which highlighted that abiotic stress impair nutrient uptake such effects can be alleviated through proper nutrient and hormonal management.

CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrated that Zinc stress adversely affected the early growth and physiological attributes of *Zea mays*. Although many of measured traits did not show statistically significant differences, clear reduction was observed in morphological attributes under Zinc stress. These findings indicate that Zinc toxicity hampers seedling establishment and overall plant vigor.

Seed growth regulators (PGRs) particularly SA and AsA showed a positive influence on growth and stress related traits. Primed seed generally maintained longer roots and shoots, greater fresh weight and higher plant pigment concentration compared with unprimed stressed seedlings. The improvement in chlorophyll, carotenoids, soluble sugars, phenolics and sulphate concentration suggests that PGRs enhanced the antioxidant capacity and metabolic activity of maize seedlings under Zinc stress.

Overall, while Zinc toxicity imposed significant challenges to maize growth, Seed priming with suitable PGRs offered a practical and low-cost approach to mitigate these effects. These findings highlight the potential of PGRs as a seed treatment strategy to enhance maize tolerance against heavy metal stress which could be valuable for improving crop establishment and productivity in zinc contaminated soils.

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